

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: FRIMPONG****FIRST NAME: MICHAEL****PROGRAM CODE: DME****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 14%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. Plagiarism as the act of using other people's materials or ideas without giving credit to the author equates to academic dishonesty and can only be remedied through in-text citation using a quotation and ----- methods.
 - Long sentences depicting an idea
 - Paraphrase¹**
 - Logical flow
 - Style guide
2. Fundamental to the design and data analysis of one's research are that

¹. Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 35.

- The methodological approach must align with the analytical approach after data collection
 - Analytical approach must align with philosophical approach of chosen methodology.²**
 - The research topic definition is dependent on need
 - Consideration is given to reviewed literature.
3. Checking for blind spots in your essays remains pivotal in revising your draft. The following actions are highly recommended except-----
- Considering the strongest relevant counterarguments
 - Just spending a lot of time polishing sentences³**
 - looking for evidence that challenges or complicates your reasons
 - Having considered alternative interpretations of your evidence.
4. Appropriate research approach is the one that best fits with your research problem. This consequently means
- There are no research problem independent and dependent variables
 - Research approaches can be manipulated to fit the problem

² Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Volpe F. Marie. *Completing your Qualitative Dissertation - A roadmap from beginning to end*. Fourth edition (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc. 2019), 269.

³ Turabian, Kate L. 2018. *A Manual for Writers of Research papers, Thesis, and Dissertation: Chicago style for students and Researchers*, 9th ed. Revised by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, The University of Chicago Editorial Staff (Chicago: University of Chicago Press. 2018), 106.

- A research problem should not be modified to fit a particular research approach⁴**
- There is a specified relationship between variables that the researcher expects to find
5. Contrary to the popular definition that a problem is a challenge to overcome, researchers think of a problem as.
- Opportunity to behold
- Research topic followed by hypothesis
- Something sought after and even invented.⁵**
- Questionable hypothesis and research method
6. In which of the following is there greater flexibility in both the methods and processes of research.
- Descriptive survey and impact studies
- Ethnography and phenomenology.⁶**
- Experimental and observation-based studies
- Expo facto and historical studies

⁴ Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Volpe F. Marie, 135.

⁵ Turabian, 29.

⁶ Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Volpe F. Marie, 169.

7. Which among the following is **NOT** related to qualitative research?
- Thematic analysis
 - Case study
 - Discourse analysis
 - Survey Method⁷**
8. Which of the mentioned research paradigms or worldviews yields itself to the statement that all knowledge can be derived from direct observation and logical inferences based on that observation?
- Post positivism⁸**
 - Pragmatism
 - Social constructivism or interpretivism
 - Critical thinking
9. Identify which of the following are carried out for constant comparison in grounded theory.
- Data collection, notetaking, open coding, and analysis⁹**
 - Data collection, data reduction, conclusion drawing, and verification
 - Data collection, axial coding, surveys, and narrative description
 - Data collection, contrasting, and generating themes and pattern

⁷ Ibid., 137.

⁸ Ibid., 146.

⁹ Ibid., 261.

10. The objective of exploring existing literature will be to identify the following except to ascertain

- What is already known about the subject area
- What concepts and theories are relevant to this area
- How to get funding for the research¹⁰**
- Inconsistencies in the findings of this area?

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Volpe F. Marie. *Completing your Qualitative Dissertation - A Roadmap from Beginning to End*. Fourth edition. Columbia University. SAGE Publications, 2019.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.

¹⁰ Ibid., 206.